

POSSIBLE ANTIAMOEBCIC AGENTS. PART II. MANNICH BASES
FROM CHLOROCHROMAN-4-ONES

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Mannich bases from 6-chloro-, 8-chloro- and 6:8-dichloro-chroman-4-ones have been prepared with a view to testing them for antiamebic activity.

In view of the close resemblance of chromanones to the naturally occurring compounds such as flavones, flavanones, chromones and coumarins and the common occurrence of the basic side chains in the therapeutically active compounds, it was deemed worthwhile to incorporate basic groups into chromanones and to study their activity on lower organisms. Wiley (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4205) has observed interesting amoebacidal activity in several Mannich bases (Ia), prepared from substituted chromanones. The presence of halogen atoms in important amoebacides, viz., vioform and diodoquin, prompted the authors to synthesise Mannich bases (Ib) from monochloro- and dichloro-chromanones with a view to studying the effect of chlorine atoms on the amoebacidal activity.

[Ia : R' & R'' = various groups]
[Ib : R' & R'' = chlorine atoms]

In the present investigation chromanones were prepared from *o*-chloro-, *p*-chloro- and 2:4-dichloro-phenols by the action of β -propiolactone (cf. Gresham *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1949, 71, 661), followed by cyclisation of the resulting β -(mono- or dichlorophenoxy)-propionic acids with either concentrated sulphuric acid (98%) (cf. Hurd and Hayao, *ibid.*, 1954, 76, 5065) or with phosphorus pentoxide in benzene (cf. Chakravarti and Dutta, *this Journal*, 1959, 16, 639).

Among the methods available for cyclisation of β -phenoxypropionic acids to chromanones, that of Hurd and Hayao, using concentrated sulphuric acid was found to be more convenient. From β -(2:4-dichlorophenoxy)-propionic acid, 89% yield of 6:8-dichlorochromanone was obtained. But in the cyclisation of β -(*o*-chlorophenoxy)-propionic acid to 8-chlorochromanone by the same method, only 28% of the cyclised product was obtained. By the method of Chakravarti and Dutta (*loc. cit.*), using phosphorus pentoxide in dry benzene, the yield was, however, improved to 76%.

The Mannich reaction in chromanones, as described by Harradence *et al.* (*J. Proc. Roy. Soc., N. S. Wales, 1939, 27, 273*) employing equimolar quantities of a chromanone, paraformaldehyde and secondary amine hydrochloride in absolute alcohol as a solvent, afforded very low yields (less than 5%) of the desired Mannich bases (Ib). But by substituting dry benzene as the solvent and acidifying the reaction mixture at the start of the reaction with a few drops of A. R. HCl and increasing the time of the reaction to 6 hours, we have obtained 80% yield of the Mannich product with 6:8-dichlorochromanone, paraformaldehyde and morpholine hydrochloride.

All the Mannich bases (as hydrochlorides) (Ib) were found to be stable, but the aqueous solutions on standing for a long time decomposed and deposited insoluble oils. The isolation of bases from (Ib) yielded sticky semi-solids which were not crystallisable. However, the bases were characterised through their picrates.

The total failure of the Mannich reaction was observed with diethylamine hydrochloride in the case of all the three chromanones used.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Chloro-, *p*-chloro- and 2:4-dichloro-phenols were distilled before use. β -Propiolactone was supplied by Eastman Kodak Company. The three β -(mono- and dichlorophenoxy)-propionic acids were obtained from the above phenols by following the method of Gresham *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

Chromanones.—The cyclisation of β -phenoxypropionic acids into chromanones was effected either by (i) H_2SO_4 (conc.) or (ii) by P_2O_5 in benzene. The method (i) used for the preparation of 6:8-dichloro- and 6-chloro-chromanones was essentially that of Hurd and Hayao (*loc. cit.*).

6:8-Dichlorochromanone.— β -(2:4-Dichlorophenoxy)-propionic acid (22 g.) was dissolved in 98% H_2SO_4 (220 c. c.). The yellow-brown solution was kept at room temperature (25°) for 36 to 48 hours, stirred occasionally, and poured over crushed ice (2 kg.), when 18 g. (89%) of the crude chromanone, m.p. 84-85°, was obtained. It was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then thoroughly with cold water. On drying and recrystallising from ethyl alcohol pure, white, crystalline chromanone was obtained, m.p. 86°-87°, yield 17 g. The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone melted at 278-79° with decomposition. (Found: N, 14.0. Calc. N, 14.1%).

6-Chlorochromanone was prepared starting from β -(*p*-chlorophenoxy)-propionic acid (21 g.) and following the same procedure, m.p. 101° (lit. m.p. 106°), yield 16 g. (84%).

8-Chlorochromanone.—The method (ii) used for preparing this chromanone was essentially that of Chakravarti and Dutta (*loc. cit.*). *o*-Chlorophenoxypropionic acid (5 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (100 c. c.) and the solution was refluxed with P_2O_5 (15 g.) for 10 hours. The supernatant benzene layer was decanted off and the brown residue was decomposed by crushed ice and then extracted with benzene. The benzene extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water and finally dried over calcium chloride. The benzene was distilled off under reduced pressure and the brown residue (3.6 g., 76%) was crystallised from alcohol in light yellow needles, m.p. 65°

3-Dialkylaminomethylchroman-4-one Hydrochlorides (Ib): Mannich Reaction.—A mixture of a chromanone (0.01 *M*) and paraformaldehyde (0.01*M*) in 25 c.c. of dry benzene was heated under reflux for 30 minutes. To this was added (0.01*M*) of a secondary or primary amine hydrochloride. (The amines used were dimethylamine, piperidine, morpholine and benzylamine hydrochlorides). The reaction mixture was acidified with a few drops of HCl and refluxed for 6 hours, during which most of the Mannich bases (Ib) separated in pure crystalline form. After cooling, the reaction mixture was filtered and the product obtained was washed repeatedly with dry benzene and finally recrystallised from absolute alcohol. The Mannich bases (Ib) were characterised by preparing their picrates.

Picrates.—The compound (Ib : 0.5 g.) was dissolved in hot water (10 c.c.) and mixed with a saturated aqueous solution of picric acid (10 c.c.). An immediate turbidity appeared and crystalline picrate separated on cooling. This was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and finally recrystallised from ethyl alcohol.

Decomposition of the Mannich Bases (Ib).—The compounds (No. 1, 6 and 11 listed in Table I) (1g. each) were dissolved separately in 10 c. c. of water. Deposition of insoluble oil was observed in each case after 36 hours' standing at room temperature.

The m. p., yield and the analysis of the Mannich bases (Ib) and their picrates are recorded in Table I.

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